

Enhancing Cognitive Radio Performance through Hybrid Sidelobe Reduction Techniques

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Abstract—Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is one of the best candidates for dynamic spectrum access due to its flexibility of spectrum shaping. However, the high sidelobes of the OFDM signal that result in high out-of-band radiation, introduce significant interference to the users operating in its vicinity. This problem becomes more critical in cognitive radio (CR) system that enables the secondary users (SUs) users to access the spectrum holes not used by the primary users (PUs) at that time. In this paper, we present a generalized OFDM framework that has a capability of describing any sidelobe suppression techniques, despite of whether one or a number of techniques are used. Based on that framework, we propose cancellation carrier (CC) technique in conjunction with the generalized sidelobe canceller (GSC) to reduce the out-of-band radiation in the region where the licensed users are operating. Simulation results show that the proposed technique can reduce the out-of-band radiation better when compared with the existing techniques found in the literature.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to fulfill the increasing demand for high data rate and wireless services and at a same time coming up with the enhanced spectrum utilization, researches from all over the world have given a suggestion to utilize the spectrum resources efficiently [1], [2]. Spectrum policy task force (SPTF) appointed from Federal Communication Commission (FCC) in its report has shown that spectrum in use of licensed user also called as PUs is most of the time idle. The idea of CR which was first given by Mitola and Maguire [3] in 1999, is the solution to the above mentioned problem. The key issue in CR is dynamic spectrum sensing (DSS) used for the activation and deactivation of the spectrum. So, efficient use of spectrum results in the precise DSS. OFDM technique [4], [5] is a high performance modulation scheme for CRs due to its ability of dividing the available bandwidth into multiple narrow band orthogonal channels, insusceptibility to frequency selective fading, efficient use of spectrum by

overlapping of subcarriers, and support for high data rate. The main challenge faced by OFDM is its sidelobes that result in high out-of-band radiation that is a cause of significant interference to the neighboring users. This is more crucial in CR systems where the un-licensed user is allowed to use the spectral hole which is not used by the licensed user at that time.

There are many techniques found in literature to tackle the problem of out-of-band radiation that are classified into two main categories: time domain and frequency domain. Time domain techniques include windowing [6], [7], filtering [8], while frequency domain techniques include CCs [9]-[11], advanced CCs [12], advanced subcarrier weightings [13], constellation expansion [14], [15], precoding techniques [16][18], and GSC [19].

In this paper, we present the generalized OFDM framework that is capable of describing any out-of-band radiation technique, and a new technique has been proposed that is a combination of CCs and GSC to reduce the out-of-band radiation effectively. The effectiveness and reliability of the proposed technique is compared with the existing techniques found in the literature, which shows that the proposed techniques show better results.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: in Sections II and III, we will discuss the system model and proposed technique, while in Sections IV and V simulations and results and conclusion of the paper are given.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider that M SUs opportunistically utilize the available spectral band identified with the help of DSS, which is unoccupied by un-licensed user. This available spectral band may be contiguous or non-contiguous in nature and can be divided into group of subcarriers. Consider n th SU employing the subgroup of subcarriers

n_r where $n_r = n_{o^r}, 1^r, \dots, n_{N^r-1}$, i.e. total number of subcarriers employed by r th SU is N_r . Also, consider that g_n is the transmitted PSK modulated symbol over the n th subcarrier. The baseband signal over the n th subcarrier with one symbol duration is given as:

$$x_r(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{N_r-1} g_n \exp(j2\pi n t / T_s) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{I} represents the identity matrix having dimension $M_r \times 1$ and $M_r \times N_r$ where

$L \times M_r \times N_r$ represents the number of CCs inserted on either sides of the OFDM signal of the r th SU, while \mathbf{Q} can be treated as precoding matrix having dimension $M_r \times N_r$ representing CCs technique defined as:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{M_r \times N_r} \\ \mathbf{I}_{N_r \times r} \\ \mathbf{B}_{M_r \times N_r} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Here, in (7), the identity matrix \mathbf{I} represents the weights of the data subcarriers, while the two matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} represent the optimized weights of the CCs. The resulting signal of r th SU will then be given by:

$$T_r = \sum_{j=1}^{\frac{M_r}{2}} f_{sj} d_{sj} + \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} f_j d_{sn} + \sum_{j=\frac{M_r}{2}+1}^{M_r} f_j d_j \quad (8)$$

The signal given in (8) has a suppressed sidelobe. For further suppression, the signal is then sampled into W_r samples and are collected in vector \mathbf{y}_r with dimension $W_r \times 1$ and passed through GSC.

GSC is the straightforward form of linearly constraint minimum variance (LCMV), which converts the minimization problem having some constraint into an unconstraint [20]. It consists of two branches, the upper one and the lower one. The upper one contains a vector called as quiescent weight vector represented by \mathbf{w}_q that preserves the incoming signal while the lower branch consists of blocking matrix \mathbf{C} followed by adaptive weight vector \mathbf{w}_a . The blocking matrix \mathbf{C} blocks the wanted portion of the signals and allows the un-wanted portion, i.e. allows the sidelobes while blocking the rest of the signal, and the adaptive weight vector \mathbf{w}_a adjusts the amplitudes of the sidelobes such that when the signal from the upper branch and lower branch are subtracted, we get a signal with a suppressed sidelobe.

The output of the GSC is given by:

$$Z_r(f) = (\mathbf{w}_q^H + \mathbf{w}_a^H \mathbf{C}^H) \mathbf{y}_r \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{d} represents the pre-coded symbol vector of r th SU

Here, in (9), the term \mathbf{w}_a is the adaptive weight vector whose function is to minimize the sidelobe that is a cause of out-of-band radiation. This adaptive weight vector modifies the amplitudes of the sidelobes such that, when the signals from the upper and lower branch subtract from each other, it will result in a signal with reduced sidelobes. The expression for \mathbf{w}_q , \mathbf{w}_a and \mathbf{C} is found in [19] is given by:

$$\mathbf{w}_q = \mathbf{C}_a^{-1} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{C}_a^{-1} \mathbf{f} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{null} & \mathbf{C}_a^H \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimized adaptive weight vector \mathbf{w}_a^{opt} is the one that minimizes the cost function given by:

$$J(\mathbf{w}_a) = \mathbf{w}_a^H \mathbf{C} \mathbf{R} \mathbf{w}_a + \mathbf{y}_q^H \mathbf{C}_a \mathbf{w}_a \quad (11)$$

i.e. $\min_{\mathbf{w}_a} \mathbf{w}_a^H \mathbf{C} \mathbf{R} \mathbf{w}_a + \mathbf{y}_q^H \mathbf{C}_a \mathbf{w}_a$ and on solving gives:

$$\mathbf{w}_a^{opt} = (\mathbf{C}^H \mathbf{R} \mathbf{C} + \mathbf{C}_a^H \mathbf{y}_q \mathbf{y}_q^H \mathbf{C}_a)^{-1} \mathbf{C}_a^H \mathbf{y}_q \quad (12)$$

Finally, we get:

$$\mathbf{w}_q^{GSC} = \mathbf{w}_q + \mathbf{C} \mathbf{w}_a^{opt} \quad (13)$$

IV. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

In this section, we consider that single SU operating in a spectrum hole detected with the help of DSS. Suppose that this SU divides the available spectrum holes into 16 sub-channels also called as subcarriers, in which e.g. a 64 – point FFT is applied for OFDM modulation. Each sub-channel is BPSK modulated whose power is normalized to 1. Here we are considering two CCs each on the left and right side of the data subcarriers. 20 sidelobes are reserved on both sides of the spectrum with one frequency sample taken

in the middle of every sidelobe, resulting in $K_l = K_r = 10$ samples. For GSC, 301 samples of the signals are collected in vector \mathbf{y} . Figs. 3-5 show the performance comparison of our proposed technique with different existing techniques found in the literature in terms of PSD that shows that our proposed technique gets better reduction of sidelobes as compared to the existing techniques.

Fig. 3 Comparison of proposed technique with existing techniques

Fig. 4 Comparison of proposed technique with existing techniques

Fig. 5 Comparison of proposed technique with existing techniques

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have given a generalized OFDM framework that has an ability of describing any out-of-band radiation reduction techniques whether we are using single or multiple techniques. Based on that framework, we have proposed a technique that is a combination of CCs' technique which can also be represented with pre-coding matrices with GSC. The usefulness and reliability of the proposed technique in term of power spectral density is compared with the other techniques found in literature, which shows that our proposed technique gets better reduction of sidelobes.

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